

Process Evaluation of the Department of Health-Center for Health Development's Oral Health Program for Older People in CALABARZON

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Abstract. The Philippines' Department of Health (DOH) recognized the importance of evaluating the oral health of older adults due to the aging population and the prevalence of dental caries and periodontal diseases. This process evaluation research examined the DOH Center for Health Development CALABARZON's implementation of the oral health program for individuals aged 60 and above, focusing on program fidelity, service target achievement, and facilitators and barriers. Data were collected through a review of published data and interviews with program managers. The analysis included content analysis of transcripts and program documents, as well as time series analysis of period data. From 2009 to 2022, the DOH reached at least 30% of the older population in half of those years. Factors that facilitated this output included an improved dentist-to-population ratio and dental missions. However, challenges, such as uneven support from local government units (LGUs), the absence of law mandating LGUs to follow oral health guidelines, and the non-inclusion of preventive dental services from PhilHealth packages, hindered access to basic oral health care. Additionally, the centrality of the Orally Fit Child program within the country's oral health framework may have detracted attention from the dental needs of older adults.

Keywords: process evaluation, oral health, aging population, dental caries, periodontal diseases

Introduction

Oral Health Among Older Filipinos

Life expectancy is increasing globally, with most people living into their sixties and beyond (Asian Development Bank [ADB], 2024), a trend also observed in the Philippines. While a longer life brings opportunities for older persons, extended lifespans can be burdensome if they live with a diminished quality of life driven by

factors like poor oral health (Amanat et al., 2020). Oral health is among the most critical and neglected health issues affecting older Filipinos (Mendoza et al., 2020; Department of Health [DOH], 2003).

Studies have shown a strong correlation between increasing age and the prevalence of oral diseases, such as dental caries and periodontal diseases (Meurman et al., 2018; Hayes et al., 2016). Dental caries, commonly called tooth decay, is a chronic disease with an infectious component prevalent worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023). The National Survey on Oral Health (NSOH) defines it as the loss of minerals and the permanent formation of cavities in the outer layer of the tooth (enamel) caused by bacterial by-products (DOH, 2019). Risk factors such as excessive sugar intake, decreased saliva production, wearing removable dentures, and insufficient fluoride exposure can lead to the formation of cavities in older individuals (Desair & Nair, 2023).

Similarly, periodontal diseases, or gum disease, were also more prevalent with age (López et al., 2017; GBD 2017 Oral Disorders Collaborators et al., 2020). It is defined by the presence of one or more of the following: gingival bleeding or gingivitis, shallow periodontal pockets, and deep periodontal pockets (DOH, 2019). Untreated periodontal disease, considered one of the direct consequences of unmet oral hygiene needs (Slack-Smith et al., 2023; Garcia et al., 2023), damages tissues and bones that support the teeth (WHO, 2023).

The Oral Health Program in the Philippines

The need to prioritize oral health can be very evident in the Philippines. The earliest recorded dental health survey on the DOH website in 1987 showed that dental caries and periodontal disease prevalence among the general population reached 94% and 66%, respectively (DOH, n.d.). A decade later, in 1998, the overall prevalence of these oral diseases remained high, with 92% for dental caries and 78% for periodontal disease (DOH, 2003). Subsequent surveys provided age-specific results, including for older individuals aged 65 to 74. In 2011, the prevalence rates for dental caries and periodontal disease among older persons were 99% and 45%, respectively (DOH, 2011). The latest survey conducted in 2018 found that the prevalence of dental caries among seniors had significantly improved to 55%. However, there was only a slight improvement in the prevalence of periodontal disease, with approximately two in five older persons suffering from at least one periodontal condition. These conditions included gingival bleeding at 44%, shallow periodontal pockets at 40%, and deep periodontal pockets at 6% (DOH, 2019).

The DOH has implemented various policies and programs to address the alarming oral health situation in the country. A dental health program was established in 1993 (DOH, 2003). This was followed by the DOH Administrative Order (A.O.) No. 101, s. 2003, or the “National Policy on Oral Health,” which outlines the guidelines on quality oral health care. Comprehensive implementation rules on the oral health program were published four years later through A.O. No. 2007-0007, also known as the “Guidelines in the Implementation of Oral Health Program for Public Health Services.” The national oral health program is designed to integrate oral health care with other health programs such as nutrition, women’s programs, and programs for older persons, ensuring the sustainable delivery of dental services.

Health service delivery and support comprise the primary components of the oral health program implementation (A.O. 2007-0007). The health service delivery

component includes providing basic oral health care (BOHC), comprising promotive, preventive, and curative services for various lifecycle groups. For instance, older persons receive an oral examination, extraction of unsavable teeth, gum treatment, pain management, and health guidance. Other critical aspects of the initial component are health education activities, a referral and follow-up system, and outreach programs in poor and hard-to-reach communities. In contrast, the support component involves health policy formulation, technical assistance to implementing units, capacity building of health human resources, collaboration with government and non-government actors, and monitoring and evaluation.

The Oral Health Program for Older Persons in CALABARZON

CALABARZON, which comprises five provinces, namely, Cavite, Laguna, Batangas, Rizal, and Quezon, and a highly urbanized city, Lucena, experienced a significant demographic shift. The population aged 60 and over grew from 12.6 million in 2010 to 16.2 million in 2020, increasing the percentage share of older persons from 6% to 8% (Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], 2012, 2022). The age transition, coupled with the alarming prevalence of dental caries and periodontal diseases among older persons in the CALABARZON and Mindoro, Marinduque, Romblon, Palawan (MIMAROPA) cluster, poses a public health concern. In 2018, the prevalence rate of dental caries among the older population in the cluster was 63% (DOH, 2019). While this was a notable improvement from the 2011 levels at 100% (DOH, 2011), it remained high. In contrast, the prevalence of periodontal diseases among older persons in the same area was 39% in 2011. The 2018 survey recorded slightly worse results, with one in two seniors having at least one gum disease. Specifically, 51% displayed gingival bleeding, 42% had shallow periodontal pockets, and 11% had deep periodontal pockets (DOH, 2019).

DOH Center for Health Development (CHD) CALABARZON seeks to improve the oral health conditions of every lifecycle group, including older persons, by 5% every year (DOH, n.d.). To attain this goal, the regional office translates the health service delivery and support components into five main strategies to which oral health activities for older persons are aligned. These strategies include advocacy, capability enhancement, service delivery, logistics, and monitoring and evaluation (DOH Regional Office IV-A, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021). Additionally, the regional office runs the Dentist Deployment Project as part of the National Health Resources for Health (HRH) Deployment Program (Abrigo et al., 2021). The dentists hired by the DOH CHD CALABARZON are deployed in the provinces or at the regional office. The regional office also provides mobile dental vehicles to LGUs, used in areas with inadequate access to dental services and to serve individuals with limited mobility.

This research aimed to examine the implementation of the DOH's Oral Health Program, which sought to improve the oral health conditions of older people aged 60 and above in CALABARZON. More specifically, this process evaluation sought to:

1. Describe the extent to which the Oral Health Program for older people in CALABARZON was implemented as planned by looking into its:
 - a. Financing
 - b. Program management
 - c. Service delivery

2. Determine the number of older people in CALABARZON who participated in the Oral Health Program by availing BOHC.
3. Identify the facilitating and hindering factors that affect the effective implementation of the Oral Health Program for older people in CALABARZON.

Framework of the Study

The logic model of the Oral Health Program for older people in CALABARZON serves as the study's analytical framework, guiding researchers in addressing evaluation objectives (see Figure 1). This logic model was based on the authors' interpretation of program information from DOH administrative orders, the DOH-CHD-CALABARZON's annual reports, and interviews with national and regional program managers. It was designed to clarify how the DOH's Oral Health Program has been implemented to enhance the oral health status of older persons in CALABARZON, serving as a valuable tool for examining program implementation. Program implementation refers to the actual execution or practice of oral health intervention. The extent to which the intervention was implemented as planned was determined by looking into the program's financing, management, and service delivery. BOHC availment was measured to indicate the success of program implementation. Factors facilitating or hindering the program's execution were assessed primarily to add context to the achievement or non-achievement of service targets.

Figure 1
Logic Model of the DOH Center for Health Development's Oral Health Program for Older People in CALABARZON

Source. Authors' interpretation based on DOH Administrative Order No. 2007-0007, DOH Administrative Order No. 101, s. 2003, DOH Dental Health Program (n.d.), DOH CHD CALABARZON annual reports, and key informant interviews.

Methodology

Evaluating health programs requires diverse methodologies (Steckler et al., 1992). This study used a mixed methods approach (Ho et al., 2021; Creswell & Clark, 2011). Quantitative data were collected to assess program financing and BOHC availment, while qualitative data were gathered to examine program management and service delivery. The results were analyzed to identify the facilitating and hindering factors affecting implementation.

Unit of Analysis

The unit of analysis in this evaluation was DOH CHD CALABARZON, the unit responsible for implementing the oral health program. The DOH CHD CALABARZON oversees the program regionally and collaborates with government entities at the national and local levels. This evaluation also highlighted the roles of the national and local governments in providing BOHC and funding to offer a comprehensive understanding of program implementation.

Sampling

Respondents and materials were deliberately selected. Two dentists were interviewed, one from the DOH Disease Prevention and Control Bureau (DPCB) and one from the DOH CHD CALABARZON (see Table 1). The former was selected for overseeing the implementation of the oral health program at the national level, while the latter was chosen for managing and implementing the program in the region. Additionally, the materials analyzed in the study included published information on the DOH's oral health program, routinely published financial data, and some recorded legislative hearing sessions that discussed the state of oral health in the country. These materials addressed the research objectives.

Table 1
Respondent Characteristics (During the Time of Interview)

Respondent Identifier	Position and Office	Years of Service in Office
Interviewee 1	Dentist, Oral Health and Nutrition Care Division, DPCB	Approximately 5 years
Interviewee 2	Dentist, Oral Health Unit, DOH CHD CALABARZON	Approximately 10 years

Data Collection

Document Review

Relevant excerpts and period data were extracted from annual reports, financial statements, and media releases. The Oral Health Program Annual Reports of DOH CHD CALABARZON from 2016 to 2021 provided the program description, strategies and action plan, health human resource statistics, and trends on the oral health conditions of the different lifecycle groups. The Field Health Services Information System (FHSIS) Annual Reports from 2009 to 2022 presented relevant statistics, such as the number of dentists, recipients of BOHC, and accomplishment of BOHC targets. Published data from the General Appropriations Act (GAA), DOH's Statement

of Appropriations, Allotments, Obligations, Disbursements and Balances (SAAODB), and Bureau of Local Government Finance's (BLGF) Statement of Receipts and Expenditures (SRE) provided financing data. The FHSIS and BLGF SRE manuals were reviewed for terms, procedures, and formulas before data utilization. Media releases and social media posts of DOH CHD CALABARZON and health centers provided context on program components. Portions of Senate legislative sessions that delved into oral health were also obtained. The hearings selected were Senate Session No. 30 on November 14, 2023, and Senate Session No. 73 on May 14, 2024. These legislative sessions provided insights into the current policy discussion about oral health.

Key informant interviews

Key informant interviews were done in person in May and June 2024. An interview guide was developed using document and literature reviews. The interview questions focused on various aspects of the program, particularly design (e.g., inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes), financing (e.g., national, regional, and local appropriations), implementation (e.g., coordination, technical assistance, service delivery), and evaluation (e.g., reporting mechanism, data sources, facilitators, barriers).

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative data were organized using Excel to facilitate time series analysis. Financing data were categorized by administrative level and presented in both actual figures and as a percentage share of total appropriations. Where possible, the data were disaggregated further into budget items that best capture the oral health budget. The agency data was broken down to the program or activity level, while local government data was presented as revenue and expenditure categories. In contrast, availment data for CALABARZON were disaggregated by sex, and trends were shown in both actual and standardized eligible populations. Differences in the formula for measuring the number of people qualified to receive program services led to data standardization to allow comparison of availment levels over the years. The mean number of beneficiaries was also measured. Gaps in data for specific years or areas were documented and recorded as study limitations. Graphs and summary tables were generated to visualize changes in financing and BOHC availment over time.

Qualitative Analysis

Relevant excerpts were extracted from pertinent documents, and interview and Senate session recordings were transcribed for further analysis. The extracted qualitative data were coded, categorized, and classified into themes using Excel. The content analysis procedure outlined by Erlingsson and Brysiewicz (2017) was employed to group meaning units that answered the objectives into relevant categories or themes for analysis. The meaning units were categorized deductively based on the research objectives, e.g., financing, program management, and service delivery. Where necessary, further abstraction of data was performed, developing themes that cut across different categories, e.g., contributions of LGUs and contributions of DOH

national. These relevant extracts, along with the pertinent literature, were used to explain program financing and describe the activities of DOH CHD CALABARZON to assess the fidelity of program implementation. These were also used to explain changes in service uptake during a given period, demonstrating the factors that facilitate or hinder the utilization of BOHC among older people.

Convergence

Quantitative and qualitative data were integrated to carry out the third research objective. The evidence from evaluating program fidelity and assessing the level of BOHC availment among older persons were analyzed simultaneously to explain the barriers and facilitators of program implementation. Specifically, the results of the time series analysis (quantitative) and content analyses (qualitative) were compared, highlighting congruent or discrepant findings (Creswell & Clark, 2011; Palinkas et al., 2011). Identifying congruences and making sense of inconsistencies in the merged evidence expanded our understanding of program implementation. For instance, both quantitative and qualitative findings in assessing program fidelity helped explain the observed trends in the level of BOHC availment (e.g., a significant drop in budget size and resourcefulness of dentists).

Ethical Considerations

This paper was written to fulfill the requirements of an academic course and was not required to undergo an ethics review by the professor. When the college's ethics review system was first implemented, only specific courses or research activities were required ethics review (e.g., thesis, dissertation, and field methods classes), and this course was not among them. Nonetheless, the researchers adhered to responsible research conduct throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained from both participants. Additionally, efforts were made to minimize potential risks and to protect participants' privacy.

Results

This mixed methods research examined the implementation of the oral health program for older persons aged 60 and above in CALABARZON. This part is divided into three sections, namely, program fidelity, availment of BOHC, and facilitators and barriers, to fulfill the study's objectives.

Program Fidelity

Financing

The national guidelines on the implementation of the oral health program presented various potential financing schemes for program implementors at the subnational levels. One of the potential sources of funding, as indicated in the guidelines, was the national government (A.O. 2007-0007, 2007). While the focus of DOH on oral health at the national level is policy development, capacity building, and advocacy, it is also the source of transfers, augmenting the financing needs of the regional-level oral health programs. Additionally, it purchases commodities, such as fluoride varnish and dental equipment, for distribution to subnational areas. The appropriations of the family health program of the DOH, which includes the funding for the oral health program, are shown in Table 2.

Table 2
*Annual DOH-Wide Family Health Budget and Percent Share to Total Budget
(in million PHP): 2012-2013, 2015-2022*

Year	Scope of Program or Activity	Appropriations (in million PHP)	Percent Share
2012	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	2,280	5.4%
2013	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	2,539	5.0%
2015	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	3,274	3.8%
2016	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	2,275	1.9%
2017	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	4,265	4.5%
2018	Family Health, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	3,640	3.4%
2019	Family Health, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	2,472	2.5%
2020	Family Health, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	2,034	2.0%
2021	Family Health, Immunization, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	12,205	9.1%
2022	Family Health, Immunization, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	9,913	5.4%

Note. The budget refers to new or current appropriations of the DOH-Office of the Secretary (OSEC). The data before 2012 and for 2014 are not available on the DOH website.

Source. GAA

While the variations in the family health appropriations can indicate changes in the oral health budget, many health priorities are merged into this line item, limiting its usefulness in gauging the level of financing for oral health. For instance, immunization was incorporated into the family health, nutrition, and responsible parenting program in 2021. However, despite the increase in funding resulting from the merging of health priorities, the budget for the line item in 2021 remained insufficient to purchase the needed COVID-19 vaccines for priority groups, such as medical frontliners (DOH, 2020, as cited in Cuenca, 2020), a deficit that would have implications for other health priorities under this line item (Cuenca, 2020). In 2021 and 2022, the funding for the oral health program is 95 million and 66 million, respectively (see Table 3). These accounted for only 0.8% and 0.7% of the family health budget.

Table 3
*DOH-Wide Oral Health Budget (in million PHP)
and Percent Share to Family Health Budget: 2021-2022*

	2021	2022
Oral Health Budget	95	66
Percent Share	0.8%	0.7%

Note. This does not include the salary of dentists or other relevant health personnel and the construction or enhancement of dental facilities included in other agency line items.

Source. DOH-DPCB

The DOH CHDs at the subnational level are also sources of financing for oral health program implementation. A part of the appropriations received by DOH regional offices are dedicated to oral health, allowing them to perform their program planning and implementation responsibilities (AO 2007-0007). The budget of the DOH CHD CALABARZON is shown in Table 4.

Table 4
*Annual DOH CHD CALABARZON Budget (in million PHP):
2014-2018, 2022*

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2022
Adjusted Appropriations	1,202	985	1,608	1,989	2,162	5,543

Note. The budget refers to new or current appropriations of DOH CHD CALABARZON. The data before 2014 is not available on the DOH website. The years missing from the table have either incomplete or unavailable data.

Source. SAAODB

The changes in the size of the regional office's appropriations did not follow the budget trend at the health program level and, in some instances, have been counterintuitive (see Table 5). The budget for family health and responsible parenting was highest in 2015 at 68.4 million, when the DOH CHD CALABARZON budget did not exceed the billion mark. The initial merging of health priorities, in which nutrition was combined with family health and responsible parenting, resulted in a lower budget for the family health line item from 15.8 million in 2017 to 10.4 million in 2018. The level of appropriations in 2022 (57.8 million) is almost six times the size of the budget for family health and responsible parenting in 2018 (10.4 million) following the inclusion of immunization into the line item, but the percent share only grew by a half percent between the years mentioned.¹

Table 5
*Annual DOH CHD CALABARZON Family Health Budget
and Percent Share to Total Budget (in million PHP): 2014-2018, 2022*

Year	Scope of Program or Activity	Appropriations (in million PHP)	Percent Share
2014	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	24	2.0%
2015	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	68	5.9%
2016	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	0.5	0.03%
2017	Family Health and Responsible Parenting	16	0.8%
2018	Family Health, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	10	0.5%
2022	Family Health, Immunization, Nutrition, and Responsible Parenting	58	0.1%

Note. The budget refers to new or current adjusted appropriations of DOH CHD CALABARZON. The data before 2014 is not available on the DOH website. The years missing from the table have either incomplete or unavailable data.

Source. SAAODB

The oral health program guidelines list local government as a source of funding. It states that LGUs should cover operational and capital expenses for the oral health program, prioritizing preventive and promotive services for children, mothers, and the poor or marginalized (AO 2007-0007). A consistent growth in the income levels of LGUs in CALABARZON can be observed from 2009 to 2020, largely due to the increase in tax revenues and internal revenue allotment (IRA; presently known as national tax allotment; see Figure 2).

Figure 2
*Local Government Unit Operating Income (in million PHP),
CALABARZON: 2009-2020*

Note. The budget refers to new or current adjusted appropriations of DOH CHD CALABARZON. The data before 2014 is not available on the DOH website. The years missing from the table have either incomplete or unavailable data.

Source. SAAODB

The operating expenditures of LGUs in CALABARZON steadily increased from 2009 to 2020 (see Figure 3), matching the growth in operating income during the period. This also corresponded to a consistent increase in expenditures for health, nutrition, and population control (see Table 6). The health, nutrition, and population control expenditure group refers to health-related spending, including medical and dental services and nutrition and family planning program administration (BLGF, 2015). The percentage share for the expenditure group has been fairly consistent over the years, ranging from 11.7% to 13.3%. A further disaggregation to estimate the size of the oral health budget is unlikely, given the variability in the priorities and activities of LGUs.

Figure 3
Local Government Unit Operating Income (in million PHP), CALABARZON: 2009-2020

Note. The operating expenditures include (1) General Public Services, (2) Education, Culture & Sports/ Manpower Development, (3) Health, Nutrition & Population Control, (4) Labor & Employment, (5) Housing & Community Development, (6) Social Services & Social Welfare, (7) Economic Services, and (8) Debt Service. The data for 2021 and 2022 are not available on the BLGF website.

Source. SRE

Table 6
Local Government Units Health, Nutrition, and Population Control Expenditure Level (in million PHP) and Percent Share to Total Operating Expenditures, CALABARZON: 2009-2020

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Expenditures	3,005	3,293	3,511	3,937	4,278	4,525	4,716	5,327	5,907	6,241	6,892	8,268
Percent Share	12.0%	11.8%	11.7%	12.2%	12.4%	12.6%	12.3%	12.7%	13.3%	13.1%	13.2%	12.6%

Note. The data for 2021 and 2022 are not available on the BLGF website.

Source. SRE

The oral health program implementation guidelines specify that patients are responsible for the costs of specific procedures like root canal treatment, prosthodontics, and orthodontics care (AO 2007-0007). The Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010 has minimized out-of-pocket payments for seniors by providing mandatory Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth) coverage for indigent older Filipinos, free dental services in public health units, and discounts for services in private facilities. Due to the Universal Health Care (UHC) Act of 2019, all senior citizens can now access PhilHealth benefits. However, the coverage only includes benefits for surgical dental procedures such as tooth extraction (PhilHealth, 2017; East Avenue Medical Center, 2017). The goal of the DOH expressed in the Administrative Order 2007-0007 to include oral prophylaxis and permanent fillings among the PhilHealth has yet to

come to fruition, but there has been interest among several legislators to make this into a reality, as evidenced during a few Senate sessions.

Program Management

The DOH CHDs play a vital role in implementing the oral health program. The 2007 guidelines on oral health program implementation enumerate regional dental coordinators' responsibilities, including policy implementation, planning and coordination, progress reporting, and evaluation (AO 2007-0007). Dental coordinators are expected to manage the program, ensuring the implementation follows DOH policies and standards. In line with their supervising function, they must craft regional plans on oral health and coordinate the program's implementation with other health priorities. They must also monitor the implementation to facilitate regular reporting of the progress and status of the operations and evaluate the program based on the DOH criteria for health service assessment.

The DOH CHD CALABARZON developed its five main strategies for implementing the oral health program: advocacy, capability enhancement, service delivery, logistics, and monitoring and evaluation (DOH Regional Office IV-A, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021). The activities of the oral health program for older persons were determined according to these five strategies, emphasizing preventive measures over curative ones. The interventions for older persons aimed to preserve remaining teeth and alleviate pain, as well as make dental services more accessible by providing them closer to the homes of older adults and integrating them into activities commonly attended by senior citizens, such as social pension payouts. The regional office also released a calendar of activities as part of its planning function. An action plan on orally fit children for 2017 to 2022 was featured in their annual reports from 2018 to 2021. It is the only lifecycle group with a corresponding action plan demonstrating the region's priorities. It also reflects national priorities, as the Orally Fit Child Program was highlighted as a central program in the implementing guidelines (AO 2007-0007, 2007). Other targeted groups are given lesser priority, a situation evident across the country.

The regional office publishes oral healthcare accomplishments annually, including the level of BOHC availment. The data source for the number of BOHC recipients was FHSIS. FHSIS consolidates the Oral Health Form 2 or the Oral Health Status and Services Report accomplished by dental units. This form is accomplished by hospitals, health units, and the CHD in varying frequencies, either monthly, quarterly, or annually. Notably, Form 2 also gives emphasis to the number of orally fit children attended. The data informed the planning of the regional dental coordinators, particularly in choosing the areas that require augmentation using regional resources. In selecting areas for dental missions, they typically chose those with low BOHC availment, usually due to the lack of dentists, and LGUs with inadequate resources, thus, unable to support oral health services. Regional criteria in selecting areas for outreach activities also consider the level of oral disease prevalence, hard-to-reach locations, absence of public dentists, and urban poor communities (DOH Regional Office IV-A., n.d.). Even in LGUs with a relatively high number of dentists, there were geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (GIDA) within their administrative boundaries that regional dentists visited.

The DOH CHD CALABARZON engaged in policy implementation by disseminating important policies, guidelines, and programs to LGUs and other health partners. This included promoting the celebration of National Oral Health Month and communicating DOH memorandums and circulars, as well as regional memorandums and advisories related to oral health (DOH Regional Office IV-A, 2023, 2024). Furthermore, the regional office published implementing rules, such as on the use of mobile dental vehicles for oral health initiatives in the communities (“Implementing policies and guidelines,” 2015).

Service Delivery

In accordance with Administrative Order No. 2007-0007, DOH CHDs are expected to provide technical assistance to dental units and facilitate the implementation of oral health initiatives with the LGUs. The DOH CHD CALABARZON implements the oral health program through various strategies, including advocacy, service delivery, capacity enhancement, and logistics.

Under the advocacy strategy, the DOH CHD CALABARZON conducted dental health missions and outreach programs that incorporate oral health education for older age groups. Specific activities included lectures on the importance of oral health and good oral hygiene, which focused on increasing their awareness of oral health problems, such as the prevalence of dental caries and periodontal diseases. Incorporated in the lectures on oral health were interactive and demonstrative activities, such as toothbrushing drills, wherein older persons were given their own oral hygiene kits and tasked to demonstrate proper ways of brushing their teeth. To maximize reach, the DOH CHD CALABARZON and LGUs sometimes integrated these oral health activities with the programs of other government offices, such as the release of assistance for indigent senior citizens and Elderly Filipino Week celebration.

Aside from these activities, DOH CHD CALABARZON promoted dental advocacies through oral health observances. In the Philippines, the National Oral Health Month is celebrated every February. This annual observance started as National Dental Health Week in 1951 but later expanded into a month-long celebration in 2004, under Proclamation No. 559. This celebration aims to strengthen public awareness of the importance of good oral health, encouraging dentists, relevant government agencies, and professional organizations to reach out to more people without access to dental services. The online webinar called the “4A SERIES: eLearning Sessions with DOH CHD CALABARZON” is a continuing initiative of the regional office to promote the National Oral Health Month celebration, as well as other oral health advocacies and services, to all age groups.

Under the service delivery strategy were the clinical help and treatments that the DOH CHD CALABARZON provided to the oral health program beneficiaries who experienced oral health problems. These clinical treatments included, but were not limited to: 1) oral examination or the visual inspection of the mouth conducted to identify oral disease; 2) oral prophylaxis and deep scaling, which refer to teeth cleaning procedures; 3) application of fluoride varnish or the treatment done to prevent or slow down tooth decay; 4) application of silver diamine fluoride (SDF), which can be used to prevent cavities from growing; and 5) restorative fillings or the repairment of damaged or missing teeth. The regional office also provided free

dentures to senior citizens in select municipalities or cities that could not finance the provision of dentures. The activities providing free dentures to older persons were funded through the DOH budget or donations.

Older adults generally benefit from oral health interventions that cater to all age groups. However, DOH CHD CALABARZON also conducted programs specifically for older persons, addressing their various health needs. Medical and dental missions for seniors were often held simultaneously, offering free healthcare services, including pneumococcal vaccination, preventive dental care, blood tests, general health assessments, and distribution of vitamin supplements and maintenance medications. Moreover, there were health centers that dedicated specific days to serving older adults and persons with disabilities (PWDs) by offering treatments and dental health kits.

In response to the population's health needs during the pandemic, the regional office also adopted teledentistry. Using online platforms like Facebook and telemedicine software, regional dentists refer patients to the nearest dentist or health unit available or provide online dental consultation if no dentists are on duty in subregional areas. The project is called the Oral Health Initiative for Dental Online Consultation or "O-HI-DOC," which connects rural health units to the regional online referral system. Teledentistry expands the population's access to dental professionals, particularly those residing in far-flung areas and those with limited mobility, like older persons.

The capacity-building strategy focused on activities seeking to develop and strengthen public dentists' knowledge and skills. Such activities include the DOH CHD CALABARZON's organization of meetings with public dentists stationed in the regional office and provinces, as well as the conduct of and attendance to training and seminars for dentists. The capacity enhancement activities organized by the regional office focus on health developments, such as the application of SDF and other dental commodities, restorative treatment for senior citizens, the impact of UHC law on dental professionals and oral health interventions, and teledentistry. The regional office conducted multiple batches of refresher courses, each comprising public dentists from different provinces. In addition to recent health developments, the training courses included planning effective oral health programs and proper ways of filling out oral health forms. Also included in the region's capability enhancement strategy was providing technical assistance to LGUs and hospitals in conducting oral health activities, especially since many areas were without dentists.

Lastly, under the logistics strategy, dental supplies and materials were provided for program activities, such as dental health missions, and for the use of the DOH CHD CALABARZON dental clinic. LGUs typically request resource augmentation from the regional office when implementing oral health interventions within their jurisdictions. The regional office responds by providing manpower, dental equipment, and commodities, such as dental kits containing toothbrushes and fluoride toothpaste. The oral health program in the region also utilized mobile dental buses, which the DOH CHD CALABARZON procures, maintains, and provides to LGUs. These dental buses were deemed significant as they help the DOH reach beneficiaries residing in remote and far-flung areas.

Availment of Basic Oral Health Care

The DOH measures the coverage of dental services provided by public primary care facilities and hospitals through the availment of BOHC. A wide variety of services compose BOHC. These include dental checkups, oral prophylaxis, dental filling, and tooth extraction (AO 2007-0007). Besides clinical care, it also covers health advocacy, such as the number of people educated on oral health. Referrals of cases that are unable to be handled by health units are also incorporated into BOHC. The number of people who received BOHC is recorded in the FHSIS.

The data on the BOHC beneficiaries were recorded initially in the 2009 annual report of the FHSIS, two years after the DOH published the implementing guidelines on the oral health program. From 2009 to 2022, an average of about 127,000 older persons received BOHC annually (see Figure 4). The availment of BOHC peaked in 2017 when around 300,000 older persons received BOHC. Across sexes, there were consistently more females who availed of the service except in 2020 and 2021.

Figure 4
Number of older persons (60+) who received Basic Oral Health Care by sex, CALABARZON: 2009-2022

Source. FHSIS

There was a substantial rise in the number of recipients yearly, starting in 2014 before reaching its peak in 2017 and dropping drastically from 2018 to 2019. The observed trend could be explained by the changes in the service target of DOH from the initial 30% of the population aged 60 and over to 100% of the old age population and vice versa (see Table 7). The eligible population or the number of people qualified to receive program services is 30% of the estimated number of older persons in an administrative area, measured by multiplying the total population by the GR factor or what appears to be the estimated population share of the target population. This method was applied from 2009 to 2012 and from 2019 to 2022. Between these two periods, the procedure was revised to make all older persons in the area qualified to receive program services, dropping the multiplier 30% from the formula.

Table 7
Methods for Estimating the Eligible Population

Period	Formula
2009-2012	Total Population x GR Factor x Service Target (30%)
2013-2018	Total Population X GR Factor (6.9%)
2019-2022	Total Population x GR Factor x Service Target (30%)

Note. The GR factor was made explicit in the FHSIS during the period 2013 to 2018; it was set to 6.9%.

During the period when the service target is 100% of the population of older persons aged 60 and above, the average number of BOHC recipients was 185,200 (see Table 8). This was almost thrice the average number of older persons who received BOHC from 2009 to 2012 and twice the average number of those who received BOHC from 2019 to 2022. However, the average proportion of OPs who received BOHC was lowest during the period 2013 to 2018.

Table 8
Data on the Size of the Eligible Population and the Number and Proportion of OPs Who Received BOHC, CALABARZON: 2009-2012, 2013-2018, and 2019-2022

Period	Average eligible population of OPs	Average number of OPs who received BOHC	Average proportion of OPs who received BOHC (%)	Actual Service Target (%)
2009-2012	235,781	59,356	25	30
2013-2018	1,014,854	185,200	18	100
2019-2022	404,110	107,822	27	30

The eligible population was standardized using the formula for 2009 to 2012 and 2019 to 2022 to make the recorded availment levels comparable over the years. In this case, the service target is 30% of the population aged 60 and above. Using the standardized measure of the eligible population, the DOH was able to serve at least 30% of the old age population (60+) in half of the years from 2009 to 2022, even exceeding the 100% mark in 2017 (see Figure 5). The proportion of BOHC availment was lowest in 2014 (15.9%), the only year the target was missed from 2013 to 2018. In contrast, the DOH did not reach the target six out of eight times from 2009 to 2012 and 2019 to 2020. The data shows that the DOH reported more cases of BOHC availment among older people when the actual service target was 100%.

Figure 5
Proportion of Older Persons (60+) Who Received Basic Oral Health Care, CALABARZON: 2009-2022

Note. The dashed lines divide the years into three periods, indicating changes in the method used to estimate the eligible population before standardization.

Source. FHSIS

Facilitators and Barriers

The results showed more females availing of BOHC than men, except in 2020 and 2021 (see Figure 4). This could be due to factors external to the program, such as the sex distribution of the CALABARZON population, in which women comprise around 60% of the old age population 60 and over based on the 2010 and 2020 censuses (PSA, 2012, 2022) and the known characteristic of older women in the Philippines that they are more likely than men to seek treatment when they have a health problem (Rodgers & Zveglich, 2021). However, the program might have also contributed to the difference in availment levels between the sexes. For instance, considering that dental missions provided by the DOH CHD CALABARZON catered to all ages instead of specific lifecycle groups, children availing of free services may have been accompanied by their grandparents who also utilized the free services. A study showed that approximately a quarter (24%) of older persons take part in providing care for their grandchildren, with notably higher involvement among women (27%) than men (19%) (Cruz & Cruz, 2019). In contrast, the reversal of the level of availment in terms of sex in 2020 and 2021 may be explained by women recording higher mobility reduction (55%) than men (41%) during the pandemic (Ancheta et al., 2023).

It is worth noting that the DOH served at least 30% of the population aged 60 and above in half of the years from 2009 to 2022 based on the standardized computation of

the eligible population (see Figure 5). The target was also only missed once from 2013 to 2018 when the actual service target was 100%. The rise in the level of availment during the period with a higher target is consistent with claims that setting targets leads to improvement in government performance (Boyne & Chen, 2007). Although there was substantial improvement in the number of BOHC recipients, the DOH CHD CALABARZON performed worse considering the proportion of older persons receiving BOHC vis-à-vis the service target from 2013 to 2018 (see Table 11). This may have prompted the reevaluation of the target, eventually lowering it. Moreover, at the national level, the budget for the family health and responsible parenting line item decreased substantially from 3,640 million in 2018 to 2,472 million in 2019, which might indicate a change in the priority level assigned to oral health.

DOH CHD CALABARZON achieved its highest proportion of older persons who received BOHC to the standardized eligible population from 2016 to 2018 (see Figure 5). When the region posted its highest level of BOHC availment (101%) in 2017, it also recorded its second lowest dentist-to-population ratio (1:63,187) since 2009 (see Figure 6). A higher number of dentists means more people can receive oral health services. This was especially noticeable during dental missions, where the participation of more dentists, both from the DOH and LGUs, allowed for the treatment of a larger number of people within a limited timeframe. The increase in the number of dentists also occurred during the expansion of the DOH HRH deployment program in 2016, leading to the inclusion of dentists in the pool of health workers hired for deployment (Abrigo et al., 2021). Hiring dentists through the Dentist Deployment Program is perceived as a critical factor in expanding the implementation of the oral health program.

Figure 6
Dentist-to-Population Ratio, CALABARZON: 2009-2022

Note. The target number of dentists to the population is 1:50,000. The ratio from 2009 to 2018 was calculated by the authors. The data for 2020 is incomplete.

Source. FHSIS

Notably, the DOH CHD CALABARZON budget for family health and responsible parenting dropped from 68 million in 2015 to a measly 0.5 million in 2016 before increasing to 16 million in 2017 (see Table 8). The achievement of the region in terms of the proportion availing BOHC in 2016 is counterintuitive given the size of the budget, but this could also be due to retaining a sizeable inventory of dental commodities from the previous years and the resourcefulness of some dentists. The latter has been credited for the achievements of LGUs in reaching the target population despite oral health not being a priority of the chief executives.

Another facilitating factor considered in the increased coverage of BOHC among older persons in CALABARZON was the LGUs and DOH's strategic integration of oral health activities with other events, such as the release of assistance for indigent senior citizens and the Elderly Filipino Week celebration. Conducting the oral health program simultaneously with such activities, where the attendance of a considerable number of older persons is expected, helped the program maximize its reach. For instance, recording the highest number of BOHC recipients in 2017 coincided with the change in the coverage of the Social Pension Program for Indigent Senior Citizens (SPISC). The age requirement for program eligibility was reduced to 60 years old and above in 2016 from 65 years and over in the previous year (Department of Social Welfare and Development [DSWD], n.d.). Considering that the dental missions for senior citizens were conducted simultaneously with the distribution of social pensions, this change in eligibility criteria might have contributed to the increase in BOHC availment.

In 2021, the region achieved its service target despite being a pandemic year (see Figure 5). Contributing factors may include the mobilization of dental vehicles coupled with the improvement in the dentist-to-population ratio in the same year (1:73,699 compared to 1:90,210 in 2020) and the implementation of teledentistry. However, the fact that, generally, only a small proportion of older persons have access to the Internet (6%) (Ogena, 2019) limits the contribution of online dental services. Additionally, there was a rise in the number of health missions, albeit mostly vaccination drives, when mobility was less restricted. Integrating dental services into medical missions could have raised the level of availment even in a pandemic year.

While the above-mentioned factors facilitated the coverage of BOHC among older persons, several factors or barriers were also found to hinder the implementation of the oral health program. One of these was the insufficient training of dentists, particularly on using available dental commodities and dental public health. The former corresponded to the issue of expiring commodities due to a lack of capacity-building on using these resources. As for the latter, dentists were said to adhere to a clinical or tooth-centered perspective rather than a public health one focusing on serving the community. This community perspective entails upstream activities, such as lobbying to formulate ordinances that allocate funds for BOHC, strengthen community action, and develop effective public health messaging (A.O. 2007-0007). Lobbying local chief executives to finance the oral health program was perceived as a weak point in implementation, thus calling for training in communication skills and strategies. The priority given by LGUs on oral health also had implications for the workforce. Some LGUs refrained from hiring dentists, while others only paid for visiting dentists. Adding to the shortage of permanent dental workforce and lack of capacity-building training was the inadequate and poorly equipped health facilities in

the LGUs that could not be fully augmented by DOH resources, all of which affected the implementation of the oral health program.

The National Monitoring and Evaluation Dental Survey (NMEDS) findings revealed that financial constraints were the main reason for individuals not seeking dental services (DOH, 2011). These economic barriers that limited access to dental care also applied to seniors. According to Natividad (2019), many older adults (86%) have unmet healthcare needs due to financial limitations. Despite the mandatory insurance coverage by PhilHealth under the UHC Act of 2019, patients, especially older individuals, still face considerable healthcare expenses. Before the enactment of the UHC, indigent older Filipinos were provided mandatory PhilHealth coverage through the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010, and all senior citizens may also avail of free dental services in public health units and discounts for services in private facilities through the law. However, the PhilHealth benefits do not adequately cover healthcare expenses, especially outpatient care (Natividad, 2019). PhilHealth covers only surgical dental procedures like tooth extraction (PhilHealth, 2017; East Avenue Medical Center, 2017).

Financial reasons were not limited to the direct costs of availing services in public health units, such as payment for anesthesia when availing tooth extraction. The reasons included the cost of transportation and travel time (DOH, 2011). Reduced mobility and transportation challenges in old age also made accessing dental services more difficult.

Dicussion

The study examined how the DOH CHD CALABARZON implemented the oral health program for older persons. It assessed program fidelity and analyzed how certain expected factors, such as those included in A.O. 2007-0007, and unexpected factors impacted the target group's utilization of dental services.

The LGUs, as the primary program implementors, have steady revenue streams, but oral health allocations vary among LGUs. Some LGUs avoided hiring dentists and offered minimal material support, similar to the NSOH report findings (DOH, 2019). Local government funding influenced the availability of municipal or city dentists, dental facilities, and related commodities, as well as the affordability of dental procedures. These allocations were also necessary to comply with the provision of the Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010, which directs the delivery of free dental services for older people. Additionally, LGUs, particularly those with high incomes, were expected to invest their resources and conduct activities on oral health. Not doing so redirected the resources of DOH CHD CALABARZON, which was earmarked for low-income LGUs and GIDAs needing resource augmentation.

It was evident from the experiences of DOH CHD CALABARZON that not all LGUs supported the oral health program, allocating resources elsewhere. Strong LGU-dentist ties were vital to direct the attention of the LGUs, which DOH often mobilized to achieve Orally Fit Child Action Plan targets, to the needs of other age groups, such as those of older people. The emphasis on the Orally Fit Child program as the central component of the dental agenda in the country may have affected the level of support for other target groups. Only the under-six children group has a regional action plan, and the oral health form accomplished by dental units requires the number of orally fit children attended.

A significant hindrance in program implementation was the absence of a law mandating LGUs to comply with the DOH's implementing guidelines despite oral health being a national priority. The DOH is the national lead agency in the health sector, but the delivery of services, including the provision of basic oral health care, is the LGU's responsibility. The DOH's actions to ensure LGUs perform their functions are limited to policy direction, regulation, and technical assistance. The lack of legislation led to variability in the implementation of the oral health program, resulting in differences in the quality of dental care across the region. A mandate proved to be a strong incentive (Boyne & Chen, 2007), as evidenced by the rise in the average number of BOHC recipients when the service target was 100%. However, it is imperative that program targets also consider the capacity of LGUs to deliver their existing functions, as larger assignments may further handicap already disadvantaged areas.

The national allocation for the DOH HRH Deployment Program contributed to sustaining and increasing the population of DOH-hired dentists (Abrigo et al., 2021). In CALABARZON, the program helped the region improve its dentist-to-population ratio. The number of DOH-hired dentists was critical in implementing the oral health program at the regional level, particularly as coordinators. Collaborative efforts among dentists also increased the ability to meet the demand for oral health services during dental interventions. Capacity development activities complemented the growth in the number of dentists. The knowledge and skills of dentists were strengthened through training on utilizing SDF and other available dental commodities, restorative treatment for senior citizens, teledentistry, and health developments relevant to seniors' oral health. Despite these activities, the 2018 NSOH reported inadequate capacity-building activities for dental professionals (DOH, 2019).

Program implementors recognized the limitations of older people in maintaining their oral health. Physical disabilities raise oral disease risk by hindering hygiene practices (Sermusuti-Anuwat & Pongpanich, 2021). Within this context, appropriate activities were implemented by DOH CHD CALABARZON to address the concerns of the target group through dental missions, health education, and teledentistry. Dental missions were particularly important for older people facing economic constraints and frailty. Health education, involving teaching older persons quality toothbrushing, was linked to improved oral health among those with disabilities (Sermusuti-Anuwat & Pongpanich, 2021). Utilizing technology and new media communications, e.g., teledentistry, also served as an essential step towards reaching a higher number of older people needing oral health interventions.

While there is interest among legislators to include preventive oral health care in the universal health care coverage and the legal basis for appropriating funds for this service is outlined in Section 6 of the UHC Act of 2019 (Mendoza et al., 2020), this has yet to happen. Including routine dental health services, e.g., oral examinations, oral prophylaxis, and fluoride varnish application, into PhilHealth coverage is viewed as a mechanism to minimize unmet healthcare needs among older people. Nonetheless, the legislators have approved the budget of DOH to purchase dental commodities, such as SDF, that consider the situation of older people. SDF is highly effective and cost-efficient in treating and preventing dental caries among older persons (Nakphu et al., 2024). The DOH has recognized this treatment and integrated its utilization into its training programs.

Limitations of the Study

The study relied on program documents describing the inputs, activities, and outputs of the DOH and LGUs and the perception of the national and regional offices. While these sources were sufficient to illustrate implementation fidelity and the level of BOHC availment, comparing the data collected from document review and interviews with inputs from local chief executives, city or municipal dentists, and other implementers at the local level could further strengthen the credibility of the collected data.

Additionally, the administrative data has limitations. First, the FHSIS contained missing or incomplete data for some provinces and cities from 2009 to 2022. This implies that the FHSIS data may not accurately reflect the actual levels of BOHC availment by older individuals from public health facilities. Second, not all annual reports prepared by government offices were available on the website, resulting in incomplete financial trends. The study was limited to documents posted in the transparency seal of pertinent government websites and provided by the agency upon the request of the researchers. This limitation of the financing data was further compounded by the lack of disaggregation by lifecycle group, although this type of reporting is unusual in the Philippines. A remedy would be to employ a budget tagging methodology, but the lack of information on the budget and activities of LGUs and their variability due to differences in income and priorities makes this unfeasible at the local level. The study resorted to selecting budget line items that best represent the oral health budget when further disaggregation is not possible.

Conclusion

The DOH CHD CALABARZON's oral health program for older persons was generally implemented as planned. Following A.O. 2007-0007, the program received support and funding from the national government, regional office, and LGUs. The DOH CHD CALABARZON translated the responsibilities outlined in the 2007 guidelines into advocacy, capability enhancement, service delivery, logistics, and monitoring and evaluation strategies, as well as implemented the activities programmed under each category. Regional dental coordinators supervised program administration, ensuring the implementation followed standards set at the national level. Furthermore, the regional office reached at least 30% of the older population in half of the years from 2009 to 2022. Contributing factors included improvement in the dentist-to-population ratio and dental missions. However, the achievement is relatively low considering the extensive program implementation across LGUs and the region's demonstrated ability to reach a higher proportion of the population during the period with a higher service target. The uneven LGU support, the absence of a law mandating LGUs to follow oral health guidelines, and the non-inclusion of preventive dental services in the PhilHealth package affected the utilization of BOHC. The availment levels might also be influenced by the centrality of the Orally Fit Child program in the country's oral health framework, affecting support for other age groups.

Future research should focus on developing a more robust theory of change that considers various assumptions that link the main elements of the logic model. The assumptions need to be clarified to fully understand how activities contribute to the reach of oral health interventions, particularly in specific groups like older

persons. For instance, DOH CHD CALABARZON's five main strategies, namely, advocacy, service delivery, capacity enhancement, logistics, and monitoring and evaluation, can achieve their desired output of reaching the service target for BOHC availment if the LGUs are doing their part. LGUs are expected to fund oral health, hire and mobilize their dentists, make dental services available in health units at no or minimal costs, conduct dental missions and health education, and integrate oral health interventions with other medical or non-medical activities. Surfacing the assumptions would improve the intervention design, particularly in pinpointing the contributing and hindering factors and identifying data needs for evaluation.

Endnote

¹ DOH CHD CALABARZON could not provide the oral health budget data requested by the researchers for the period covered by the study. However, the regional office's Work and Financial Plan for 2023 and 2024 disclosed that the requested budget for oral health-related activities amounted to 3.4 million pesos in 2023 and 3.6 million in 2024 (DOH Regional Office IV-A, 2023, 2024).

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